

SOME ASPECTS OF STUDYING TRANSPORT CORRIDORS IN SYSTEM OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

Kh.M. Azimov

Researcher of the Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies

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***Abstract.** There is no unified definition of a transport corridor in the scientific literature, due to the interdisciplinary nature of the phenomenon. The increasing pressure on existing international transport routes is accompanied by a decline in their efficiency, rising costs and the risk of loss of sustainability, which poses a particular threat to the stability of international trade. These trends highlight the need for a thorough theoretical and methodological analysis of the concept of a "transport corridor" as a systemic category integrating geographic, economic, legal and infrastructural aspects.*

***Keywords:** integrating geographic, economic, legal and infrastructural aspects.*

There is no unified definition of a transport corridor in the scientific literature, due to the interdisciplinary nature of the phenomenon. The increasing pressure on existing international transport routes is accompanied by a decline in their efficiency, rising costs and the risk of loss of sustainability, which poses a particular threat to the stability of international trade[1]. These trends highlight the need for a thorough theoretical and methodological analysis of the concept of a "transport corridor" as a systemic category integrating geographic, economic, legal and infrastructural aspects.

According to the works of several researchers, a transport corridor is "a set of agreements aimed at changing the speed and direction of flow within a given space"[2]. This interpretation shifts the emphasis from physical infrastructure to management and coordination mechanisms that ensure the efficient movement of goods and passengers. This approach reflects the evolution of views on transport as a system of not only physical but also institutional interactions[3].

Another group of researchers focuses primarily on the material and technical aspects of the functioning of transport corridors, examining them through the prism of infrastructure and the modes of transport used. This approach has become widespread in European transport practice and was enshrined in the definition of a transport corridor formulated at the pan-European transport conferences of 1993-1994. According to this document, a transport corridor is understood as "a set of trunk transport communications (both existing and newly created) with the corresponding facilities and infrastructure, linking major transport hubs, within which various modes of transport are used, ensuring the carriage of passengers and goods in international traffic in the direction of their greatest concentration"[4]. This position reflects the traditional infrastructure paradigm, within which the key parameters of a transport corridor are throughput capacity, technological equipment and the integration of various modes of transport.

Some research schools interpret international transport corridors primarily as geographic spaces and linear infrastructure facilitating the movement of goods and people, while others view them as institutionally defined routes shaped by norms, agreements and political understandings. In this regard, this dissertation adopts the approach that a transport corridor represents a complex spatial-institutional structure that integrates infrastructure, transit agreements, logistics hubs,

regulatory regimes and international cooperation mechanisms. This approach allows for the study of international transport corridors not only from the perspective of logistical efficiency but also through the lens of political economy and international security theory.

The concept of an international "transport corridor"[5] is a subject of debate among researchers, economists, and representatives of international organizations. In the classical sense, an international transport corridor is a system of transport routes, including road, rail, sea and air routes, connected by logistics hubs, terminals, and checkpoints. This approach is widely accepted by international institutions regulating transport logistics, including the International Maritime Organization, the International Road Transport Union and the International Civil Aviation Organization. According to their interpretation, an international transport corridor facilitates the physical movement of goods, services and people between economic centers, reducing logistics costs and increasing the efficiency of global supply chains.

However, in recent decades, transport corridors have come to be viewed not only as an element of infrastructure, but also as an important factor in geopolitical and geoeconomic competition. In this context, international transport corridors are acquiring strategic significance, becoming a tool of economic influence and a factor in global logistics competition. This approach is particularly evident in China's Belt and Road Initiative [6], the North-South project [7] and the European Union's TEN-T strategy [8] aimed at developing a trans-European transport network.

L. Albrechts and T. Coppens view a transport corridor as a system of physical or virtual infrastructure that connects key logistics hubs in Europe[9]. In their interpretation, transport corridors play the role of strategic routes that facilitate the integration of transport networks and improve the efficiency of freight and passenger transportation between the region's main economic centers. They emphasize the need for a balance between mobility and spatial development, emphasizing that the effective functioning of transport corridors requires not only infrastructure investments but also coordinated territorial planning strategies. Excessive concentration of investment in certain corridors can lead to territorial segregation, with less developed regions excluded from international transport flows. Albrechts and Coppens' ideas can be adapted to the analysis of international transport corridors in Central Asia, where integrating infrastructure projects with regional spatial development is a key objective. The development of corridors such as the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route (TCITR), the China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan railway, and the North-South Corridor is leading to the formation of new economic hubs, altering logistics flows, and transforming the regional landscape. Applying the concept of "space of flows," international transport corridors can be viewed not only as means of transit but also as a factor facilitating territorial development and the emergence of new economic centers. For example, increased integration of Central Asian transport infrastructure with European and Asian markets could lead to a redistribution of freight flows and a shift in traditional trade routes.

Western researchers analyze the nature of transport corridors, consider the key participants influencing their functioning, identify the main goals of their creation and development, and address a number of other conceptual issues related to their evolution and management[10]. Several key components of transport corridors are identified that determine their functioning and development. Firstly, these are the participants in the transport process, including public and private structures regulating and operating transport networks. Secondly, this is the economic and logistical infrastructure necessary for organizing sustainable flows of goods and passengers. Thirdly, these are the regulatory and legal mechanisms that determine the operating conditions of the corridors, including customs procedures, technical standards, and safety issues. Fourthly, these

are environmental and spatial factors, which are becoming increasingly significant in the context of tightening international norms on sustainable development. An important contribution of the authors is the analysis of the goals of the creation and development of transport corridors. They view corridors not only as means of ensuring transport connectivity between regions, but also as tools of spatial policy that facilitate the redistribution of economic activity and the integration of territories into global trade systems.

Historically, transport corridors have evolved based on the technological capabilities and economic priorities of specific eras. In ancient times, key trade routes such as the Silk Road[11] and the Hanseatic League[12] served as the foundation of international economic ties, determining the development vectors of civilizations. The Hanseatic League was a powerful trading association of northern European cities that existed from the 13th to the 17th centuries[13]. This association arose in response to the need to protect trade interests and ensure safe routes for merchants transporting goods across the Baltic and North Seas. Unlike centralized states, the Hanseatic League functioned as a decentralized confederation of trading cities, where decisions were made collectively at special meetings called Hanseatic Days. The main goal of the Hanseatic League was to create a unified economic space free from feudal duties and piracy. To this end, the Hanseatic League member cities entered into agreements establishing uniform trade standards, weights, and tariffs. The League encompassed over 200 cities, including Lübeck, Hamburg, Bremen, Riga, Tallinn and others. It promoted the development of trade infrastructure, the construction of ports and warehouses and the establishment of trade missions in strategically important locations across Europe. One of the most important achievements of the Hanseatic League was the creation of a reliable transportation network linking Northern Europe with the key markets of England, the Netherlands, France, and Scandinavia. However, by the 17th century, with the rise of nation states and the development of alternative trade routes, the League's influence began to wane and by the early 18th century, it had effectively ceased to exist. The Hanseatic League can be seen as one of the earliest forms of regional cooperation in Europe. This association operated on the principle of mutual agreements, where member cities provided each other with preferential terms of trade, the safety of sea and land routes, and also protected collective economic interests.

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